

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY IN CLIMATE CHANGE CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Climate change is one of the biggest challenges facing the global economy today, which can pose risks to financial stability. There are increasing regulations regarding environmental protection, which require the activation of a sustainable economy in the country and the introduction of sustainable practices from businesses so that companies are prepared to meet the new regulations and avoid potential fines.

Keywords: climate, sustainable economy, financial stability, taxonomy and green loans.

Climate change is one of the biggest challenges facing the global economy today, which can pose risks to financial stability. Climate change is a significant and long-term change in global average weather and temperature. It can be caused by both natural internal processes and anthropogenic, that is, as a result of human activity and action. Today, the current term "climate change" refers to anthropogenic climate change. It is already internationally recognized that climate change is a source of financial risks, and these risks arise for two main reasons: 1. Physical damage caused by climate change, i.e. physical risk, and 2. Structural changes required to transition to a low-carbon economy, i.e. transition risk.

Physical risks refer to the direct and indirect impacts of climate change on business and the economy due to extreme natural events and changes in environmental conditions. Physical risk is considered acute when it is manifested by climate and weather-related events. For example, such as drought, flood, storm and others. A physical risk is chronic if it is caused by gradual climate changes such as global warming and sea level rise. A source of physical risk can be a direct result of these events, such as property damage or a drop in productivity, although it can also be an indirect result of such consequential events as supply chain disruptions. For example, an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme natural events such as hurricanes, floods, landslides, wildfires can damage property, infrastructure and assets, resulting in financial losses for businesses and households. Also, changes in temperature and precipitation, prolonged drought or extreme heat can affect agricultural productivity and yields, which in turn is reflected in increased food prices. However, climate-related events can disrupt supply chains, manufacturing facilities, transportation networks or damage key suppliers, causing delays and increased costs for companies. Physical risks, if realized, entail significant financial losses that can affect both macro and broader systemic levels.

Transition risk is associated with the transition to a low-carbon and climate-resilient economy. It arises from changes in the price of depreciated assets, and in

the process, changes in climate-related policies and regulations, technology and market sentiment, and associated economic disruptions.

Regulations aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting the development of renewable energy or introducing a carbon tax can directly affect fossil fuel-dependent industries, leading to asset depreciation and reduced profitability.

Consumer attitudes toward green and environmentally friendly products and services may change, affecting demand and potentially affecting the revenues of companies that fail to adapt to new market demands.

Physical and transitory risks affect the macroeconomic environment and may cause significant financial losses. Accordingly, identification, study and management of these risks are necessary for companies' investors, financial institutions regulations and policy makers to ensure the stability and sustainability of the economy and financial sector under climate change conditions. Payday loans are of great importance to avoid the mentioned circumstances.

A green loan is a loan whose amount is exclusively used to finance green activities, that is, economic activities that have a positive impact on the environment. Be it renewable energy production, energy efficient buildings, or green transportation. The Green Loan provides the financial support needed to implement these projects. More specifically, how to determine for which activity to take a green loan, that is, what can be considered a green activity, the National Bank of Georgia has developed a taxonomy of sustainable financing with the involvement of a number of local and international experts. A taxonomy is a classification system that assigns green status to economic activities that meet certain criteria. The green taxonomy includes a list of activities that contribute to the achievement of environmental protection goals and the development of a green economy. More specifically, the Green Taxonomy covers 11 key categories: renewable energy, energy efficiency, waste management, sustainable water management, pollution prevention and control, green transportation, sustainable agriculture, biodiversity conservation, green construction, sustainable manufacturing and trade, and green services. Each of these main categories is divided into categories and subcategories,

and a total of 105 different activities are defined in the Green Taxonomy. In other words, the taxonomy is a catalog of green activities that financial institutions and companies can use to identify projects eligible for green credit.

What are the advantages of green activities and how to use them, in particular, why should we take a green loan?

In the practice of green technologies, it is expected that investments in the long and medium term will be reflected in saving resources, reducing costs and increasing efficiency.

Companies are increasingly aware of the risks associated with climate change, resource scarcity and environmental degradation. Investing in sustainable projects through green loans will help mitigate these risks, ensuring the company's long-term viability and resilience. For example, implementing climate-smart agricultural practices enables farmers to mitigate the risks associated with extreme natural events (floods, droughts, hail) and reduce financial losses caused by them.

Implementation of environmentally friendly practices will have a positive impact on the company's reputation and market positioning. Consumers and investors increasingly prefer green and sustainable manufacturing businesses. Therefore, taking out green loans can be a strategic move to respond to these changing sentiments on the part of consumers and investors. However, the use of green technology and practices often

involves innovation. Companies that lead in green initiatives can establish themselves as industry innovators, gain competitive advantage and access to new markets, and attract responsible customers and investors.

As we mentioned, green loans are intended to finance projects that have a positive impact on the environment. By implementing such projects, companies can contribute to the sustainable development of the country, reduce the ecological footprint and demonstrate the company's high social and environmental responsibility.

So, to sum up all of the above, it is necessary to highlight the role of a sustainable economy in changing climate conditions, because at this time there are financial, strategic and environmental reasons why we should invest in green projects and therefore take out a green loan.

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